

Complex-Moment Invariant Descriptors for Enhancing ResNet50-Based Breast Cancer Mammography Classification

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Abstract Breast cancer screening relies on mammography, yet automated diagnosis remains challenging due to subtle lesion appearance and acquisition variability. While deep CNNs achieve strong performance, geometric invariance is typically learned implicitly. This paper proposes a hybrid framework integrating similarity-invariant descriptors derived from complex moments with deep convolutional features. The descriptors cancel translation, rotation, and isotropic scaling, and are fused with an ImageNet-pretrained ResNet50 via lightweight late fusion without modifying the backbone. Experiments on CBIS-DDSM using stratified 5-fold cross-validation achieve **94.8%** accuracy and **0.938** AUC, a +3.6% gain over the baseline.

Key words: Breast cancer, Mammography, ResNet50, Complex moments, Invariant descriptors, Feature fusion, Binary classification.

1 Introduction

Breast cancer is a leading cause of mortality among women, and mammographic screening remains the primary early detection strategy [9]. Deep CNNs have become dominant in medical image analysis, with residual architectures providing strong baselines for mammographic classification [6,12]. The CBIS-DDSM dataset [8] enables reproducible evaluation of automated methods.

However, standard CNNs guarantee only translation equivariance. Robustness to rotation and scale is encouraged through augmentation, yet networks remain sensitive to small geometric perturbations [1] - a critical issue in full-mammogram settings

where breast positioning varies across acquisitions. Analytic moment-based invariants [7,13] offer a principled alternative with mathematically guaranteed stability under similarity transforms [3].

In this work, we integrate complex-moment similarity invariants [4] with ResNet50 deep features via lightweight late fusion. Contributions: (i) compact descriptors canceling translation, rotation, and scale; (ii) late-fusion scheme without altering the backbone; (iii) robustness study under geometric and noise perturbations; (iv) validation on CBIS-DDSM with consistent gains.

2 Proposed Method

The framework, shown in Fig. 1, combines a CNN branch and an invariant branch.

Preprocessing. Images are normalized to $[0, 1]$ via min-max scaling. A negative transformation $f'(x, y) = 1 - f(x, y)$ is applied when the global mean intensity is below 0.5 to ensure consistent polarity, as moment descriptors are sensitive to intensity inversion [4]. Images are resized to 224×224 for the CNN and 128×128 for invariant extraction.

Similarity-invariant descriptors. Complex moments are defined as [4]:

$$c_f(p, q) = \iint (x + iy)^p (x - iy)^q f(x, y) dx dy. \quad (1)$$

Under similarity transforms (scale a , rotation b): $c_g(p, q) = a^{-(p+q+2)} e^{-i(p-q)b} c_f(p, q)$. Using $\Theta_f = \arg c_f(1, 0)$ and $\Gamma_f = \sqrt{c_f(0, 0)}$, the similarity-invariant quantities are:

$$I_f(p, q) = \Gamma_f^{-(p+q+2)} \exp[-i(p-q)\Theta_f] c_f(p, q). \quad (2)$$

Stacking $|I_f(p, q)|$ for $p + q \leq N_{\max} = 10$ yields a 66-dimensional descriptor.

Late-fusion architecture. ResNet50 [6] produces a 2048-dim embedding projected to $h_{\text{cnn}} \in \mathbb{R}^{512}$. The invariant vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^{66}$ is embedded by a two-layer MLP ($66 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 64$) to $h_{\text{inv}} \in \mathbb{R}^{64}$. Both are concatenated and classified:

$$h = [h_{\text{cnn}} \| h_{\text{inv}}], \quad \hat{y} = \sigma(g(h)), \quad (3)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ is a FC head ($576 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 2$) with batch normalisation and dropout (rate = 0.5).

Figure 1 – Proposed pipeline: ResNet50 deep features fused with complex-moment invariant descriptors via late fusion.

3 Experiments

We evaluate on CBIS-DDSM [8] (benign vs. malignant, 1 566 patients, ≈ 892 benign / ≈ 674 malignant) using patient-wise stratified 5-fold cross-validation. Three configurations are compared: (i) ResNet50 baseline, (ii) ResNet50 with negative preprocessing, (iii) full late-fusion model. Training uses Adam ($\text{lr} = 10^{-4}$, batch = 16, 50 epochs), early stopping (patience 5), and learning-rate reduction on plateau (factor 0.5, patience 3). Random horizontal flips are applied to CNN inputs only; invariant descriptors require no augmentation.

4 Results and Discussion

Table 1 reports performance. Negative preprocessing alone yields +1.6% accuracy, confirming the importance of photometric normalisation for moment computation. The full model achieves **94.8%** accuracy, **0.948** F1, and **0.938** AUC — a +3.6% gain over the baseline.

These results demonstrate that each component of the proposed pipeline contributes meaningfully to the final performance.

The ablation study reveals a clear additive effect: negative preprocessing improves

Table 1 – Performance on CBIS-DDSM (benign vs. malignant). Best results in **bold**.
[†]External methods may use different splits.

Method	Acc.	F1	AUC
<i>Literature</i> [†]			
ResNet50 [11]	0.901	0.900	0.919
ResNet50+SVM-RBF [2]	0.924	0.916	–
Wavelet-CNN [5]	0.850	–	–
Ours (5-fold CV, mean±std)			
ResNet50 (baseline)	0.912 ± 0.008	0.893 ± 0.011	0.904 ± 0.010
ResNet50 + Neg.	0.928 ± 0.007	0.922 ± 0.009	0.912 ± 0.008
ResNet50 + Inv.	0.931 ± 0.006	0.938 ± 0.007	0.931 ± 0.008
ResNet50 + Neg. + Inv. (Ours)	0.948 ± 0.006	0.948 ± 0.007	0.938 ± 0.008

photometric consistency and yields a +1.6% accuracy gain, while the integration of invariant descriptors provides an additional +2.0% improvement. This confirms that analytic geometric invariance carries complementary discriminative information that deep features alone cannot capture implicitly. Notably, the AUC improvement from 0.904 to 0.938 indicates better ranking quality across all operating thresholds, which is particularly relevant in clinical screening scenarios where the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity must be carefully managed. Furthermore, the consistent low standard deviation across folds (≤ 0.008) confirms the stability and reproducibility of the proposed approach under different patient splits.

Compared to external methods in the literature, our approach achieves competitive results. While ResNet50+SVM-RBF [2] reaches 0.924 accuracy using multi-context fusion with a support vector machine, our method surpasses it by +2.4% through a simpler and more principled integration of analytic invariants, without requiring separate feature extraction pipelines.

Figure 2 confirms stability of descriptor magnitudes under rotation and scaling, with minor residual errors due to discretisation [3]. Noise causes a gradual increase in relative error, reflecting numerical sensitivity rather than an invariance violation [4].

Figure 2 – Invariant stability under rotation (left), scaling (centre), and Gaussian noise (right).

Figure 3 shows that polarity inversion collapses descriptor magnitudes despite unchanged geometry, explaining the +1.6% gain from polarity correction.

Figure 3 – (a) Mammograms before/after preprocessing; (b) descriptor collapse under polarity inversion.

5 Conclusion

We proposed an invariant-guided framework fusing complex-moment descriptors with ResNet50 features via late fusion, providing explicit invariance to translation, rotation, and scaling without modifying the backbone. On CBIS-DDSM, our method

achieves +3.6% accuracy and improved AUC over the baseline. Robustness analyses confirm geometric stability under similarity transforms and moderate noise, while highlighting sensitivity to photometric inversion. Future work will address photometric-robust descriptors and cross-dataset validation on INbreast [10].

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